

Comparative variation in physico-chemical properties and heavy metals estimation of drinking water samples collected from different districts of Jharkhand, India and their water quality index[†]

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Abstract : Water resource shortage and pollution has seriously threatened the survival and development of developing countries. Because of India's specific economical and social circumstances, complete adoption of developed countries experience is unrealistic. At present, India needs to develop strategies and technologies in source water pollution control and industrial and municipal environmental remediation that embrace the country's specific need to battle the water resource problem. This study was aimed to comparative variation in physico-chemical properties and heavy metals estimation of drinking water samples collected from different districts of Jharkhand, India and their water quality index. A total number of 28 water samples were collected from different sources like hand pumps, wells and taps. The gross appearance, pH, total hardness, Ca, Mg, total alkalinity, Na, K, Cl⁻, SO₄⁻, NO₃⁻, F⁻, TDS and heavy metals like Cu, Pb, Zn, Ni, Cd, Cr, Mn and Fe were analyzed. The results of physico-chemical parameters and heavy metals estimation of most of the water samples were found to be within acceptable limit as per IS-10500 and some of the samples from district Dhanbad, Bokaro, Ramgarh, Hazaribag area and Giridih showed slight variation from IS-10500. WQI value indicates that quality of water from all five districts is poor. The ground water for use of drinking purpose requires some treatment including removal of iron and softening.

Keywords : Water resource, physico-chemical properties, heavy metals. WQI.

Introduction

Water of good drinking quality is of basic importance to human physiology and man's continued existence depends on its availability¹. The provision of potable water to the rural and urban population is necessary to prevent health hazards². Ground water is generally considered as safe source of fresh drinking water³. But rapid population growth, increasing living standards in urban areas and industrialization have resulted in greater demand of quality water on one hand, while on the other hand pollution of water sources is increasing steadily. Therefore the ground water is getting polluted among which wells are generally considered as worst type of ground water sources in the term of physico-chemical contamination due to the lack of concrete plinth and surrounding drainage system^{4,5}. The incidence of ground water pollution is highest in urban areas where large volumes of waste discharged into

relatively small areas⁶. There are various factors, which are responsible for ground water contamination such as use of fertilizer in farming⁷, seepage from effluent bearing water body⁸. Once the groundwater is contaminated, its quality cannot be restored by stopping the pollutants from the source. Therefore it becomes imperative to regularly monitor the quality of groundwater and to device various means to protect it⁹. The surface water sources, in general, are not acceptable for drinking purpose as these are often loaded by various organic, inorganic and biological constituents^{10,11}.

In the recent years, the availability and access to fresh water has become the most critical issue in the world. Freshwater is essential to human health, agriculture, industry and natural ecosystems, but is now running scarce in many regions of the world¹². The desirable properties of water quality should include adequate amount of dis-

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

solved oxygen, relatively low organic content, pH value near neutrality, moderate temperature, and free from excessive amount of infectious agents, toxic substances and mineral matter¹³. Potable water should be free from disease producing microorganisms and chemical substances that are dangerous to health¹⁴. Majority of the rural people do not have access to potable water and therefore, depend on well, stream and river waters for domestic use. Excessive use of limited water resources, disposal of various industrial effluents, human wastes into water may release heavy metals, which harm both human and animals health¹⁵. Continuous exposure to heavy metals on animals and humans cause hepatotoxicity and nephrotoxicity. So, periodical estimation of level of heavy metals in water is necessary. In the present communication authors were focused on comparative variation in physico-chemical parameters and heavy metals estimation of drinking water samples collected from Dhanbad, Bokaro, Giridih, Hazaribag and Ramgarh districts of Jharkhand and their WQI.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

A total of 28 samples were randomly taken from different sources like hand-pumps, wells and taps in month of October 2015-January 2016.

Monitoring sites :

In the present study, total 16 sites from different districts of Jharkhand were selected for the physico-chemical analysis and heavy metals estimation of drinking water (Table 1, Fig. 1).

Sample collection :

The samples collected and stored in thoroughly washed and sterilized bottle and brought to the laboratory for detailed physico-chemical analysis and heavy metals estimation.

Sample preservation :

The water samples are collected in a separate clean bottle and acidified with nitric acid to a pH below 2.0 to minimize precipitation and adsorption of certain cations such as aluminum, cadmium, copper, iron, lead, manganese, silver and zinc. To minimize the potential for volatilization or biodegradation between sampling and analysis, the samples are kept as cool as possible without freez-

Table 1. Water quality sampling site

Site no.	Site name	District	Total no. of samples
Site 1	Rohrabnadh	Dhanbad	2
Site 2	KD/FD Colony		2
Site 3	BIT Campus		2
Site 4	Sharpura		2
Site 5	Domgarh		2
Site 6	ACC Factory		2
Site 7	Angwali Village	Bokaro	2
Site 8	Khero Village		2
Site 9	Chilga Village	Giridih	2
Site 10	Paperwahtand Village		2
Site 11	Layio Village	Hazaribag/Ramgarh	1
Site 12	Hurdag Village		1
Site 13	Kedla Township		1
Site 14	Basantpur Village		1
Site 15	Saunda Village	Ramgarh	2
Site 16	Jarjara Village		2

ing. If immediate analysis is not possible samples were stored at 40 °C. Most of the preservation methods are pH control, chemical addition, refrigeration, filtration and freezing¹⁶.

Physico-chemical parameters :

It is very essential and important to test the water before it is used for drinking, domestic, agricultural or industrial purpose. Water must be tested with different physico-chemical parameters. Selection of parameters for testing of water is solely depends upon for what purpose we going to use that water and what extent we need its quality and purity. Water does content different types of floating, dissolved, suspended and microbiological as well as bacteriological impurities. Some physical test should be performed for testing of its physical appearance such as temperature, color, odour, pH, turbidity, TDS etc., while chemical tests should be perform for its alkalinity, hardness and other characters. For obtaining more and more quality and purity water, it should be tested for its trace metal, heavy metal contents. It is obvious that drinking water should pass these entire tests and it should content required amount of mineral level. Only in the developed countries all these criteria's are strictly monitored. Due to very low concentration of heavy metal and organic pesticide impurities present in water it need highly sophisti-

Fig. 1. Water sampling locations.

cated analytical instruments and well trained manpower. Following different physico-chemical parameters are tested regularly for monitoring quality of water. These parameters were determined by using standard procedures, APHA¹⁶.

Gross appearance, odour and taste : The water samples were observed with naked eyes for gross appearance and examined for offensive odour through the subjective organoleptic assessment.

pH : pH is termed as negative logarithm of the H_2 ion concentration. The pH is determined by Elico, digital pH meter which gives direct values of pH.

Conductivity : The conductivity is determined by using digital conductivity meter.

Temperature : A mercury filled centigrade thermometer calibrated from 0 to 100 °C is used for temperature measurements.

Turbidity : It can be determined by using turbidity meter (Delux turbidity meter, ESICO International, Model no. 335, Sr. No. 1401551, India).

Total hardness : Fifty milliliters of water sample is titrated against 0.01 M EDTA (disodium salt) solution by using Solo chrome Black T as an indicator.

Total alkalinity : The alkalinity of water sample is determined by titrating it against standard acid solution using indicators like phenolphthalein and methyl orange.

Chloride content : The chloride content in the water sample is determined by titrating the water sample against 0.02 M silver nitrate solution using potassium chromate as an indicator.

Sulphate content : Sulphate content in the water sample is determined by turbid metric method.

Nitrate content : UV light having 220 nm wave length is passed through the sample. The absorbance obtained is

Fig. 2. Comparative variation in physico-chemical properties and heavy metals estimation of drinking water samples collected from different districts of Jharkhand, India.

Table 3. Water quality index

Index value	Water quality
< 50	Excellent
50–100	Good
100–200	Poor
200–300	Very poor
> 300	Unfit for drinking

ferent concentration of cations and anions in the water. Regular estimation of the above mentioned parameters would be helpful to improve water quality. The study will be utilized for designing the best management practices as per standard regulations. It will help for development of basis for effluent trading. The use of ground water for industrial purpose does not appear techno-economically

Table 4. Water quality index value of different districts of Jharkhand

Parameters	Acceptable limit as per IS-10500	Unit	Districts	WQI value	Water quality
pH	7.5	0.0314488	Dhanbad	142.5	Poor
TDS	500	0.0012682	Bokaro	195.2	Poor
TH	200	0.0032524	Giridih	187.0	Poor
NO ₃	45	0.0067248	Hazaribag/Ramgarh	184.0	Poor
F	1	0.2141488	Hazaribag/Ramgarh	183.0	Poor
Fe	0.3	0.7431558	Ramgarh	189.0	Poor

The WQI value of water samples collected from all five districts ranges from (142.5–195.2) and water quality is found to be poor which is mainly due to high Fe concentration¹⁷ (Tables 3 and 4). The variation in water quality is primarily due to the various stages of metamorphism of Gondwana rocks present in this locality. According to Stumm¹⁸ water flowing through different rocks have dif-

ferent concentration of cations and anions in the water. Regular estimation of the above mentioned parameters would be helpful to improve water quality. The study will be utilized for designing the best management practices as per standard regulations. It will help for development of basis for effluent trading. The use of ground water for industrial purpose does not appear techno-economically

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